

CNN-based Image Retrieval System

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Abstract — The goal of this paper is to develop an image search and similarity founding system using convolutional neural network model. The implementation of this model will be done using the TensorFlow and NumPy libraries. When using a regular search engine, text search can often provide a wide range of products, but they may not be similar to what we are looking for. This can be frustrating and time-consuming. A better solution is to use content-based image retrieval technology, which allows us to retrieve similar products based on an image query. This system works by extracting features from all images in the database, including the query image, using a feature extraction algorithm. Similarities are then calculated between the query image and all images in the database, and the system retrieves all images that have a high degree of similarity with the query image. This technology provides a more efficient and accurate way of finding products that match our preferences.

Keywords- Image Search, TensorFlow, Numpy, Deep Learning, Content-based image retrieval

I. INTRODUCTION

An image-based search engine is a search engine that allows users to search for images using visual content rather than text-based queries. In image based search engines the resultant image is based on the similarity with the query image. These kind of search engine is very powerful comparing with the normal text search in this time because we always focus on accuracy and less time consuming tasks. In this paper, we present an approach to develop an image based search engine using convolutional neural network with numpy and tensorflow libraries.

In the rise of using social medias and other online platforms now people have more expose with visual contents so they prefer to an image-based search rather than text search. Image-based search in ecommerce websites is very helpful to find the similar products effectively. In the image-based search, customers upload a query image that they want to search and the sites displays the similar images with respect to the query image. This helps the customers to search the products that they want, quickly and easily, without searching for a longtime with a specific keyword.

Computer vision technology, which recognizes and examines the visual aspects of images using machine learning and artificial intelligence, is the foundation of image-based search in e-commerce. This technology is able to identify particular characteristics like colour, texture, size, and form, and then compare those characteristics to those of similar products on e-commerce websites.

Image-based search can help websites increase sales and become more user-friendly in addition to making it simpler for buyers to search for a specific product within the dataset. By providing a more user-friendly option to searching for a particular product it enhance the customer needs and repeat business.

This approach use a wide range of image datasets from the project database to find whether the searched product is found or not in the system. Here preprocessing is an important process in Deep Learning as it involves processing of the raw data into a specified format that can be transform into the neural network. The preprocessing have several steps like resizing, normalization, and cropping of images. Then we want to extract the features from the images using CNN. CNNs are used to learn features from images automatically by using convolutional and pooling layers. The output of these layers is then flattened and fed into a fully connected layer to generate a feature vector for each image. The feature vectors obtained in the previous step are then indexed using a suitable indexing method. When a query image is received, the same feature extraction process is performed, and the resulting feature vector is used to search for similar images in the indexed dataset. The last step involves arranging the search results based on the similarity between the query image and the images in the dataset. The similarity of the images can be calculated using several methods like Euclidean distance.

A. Nature of Convolutional neural network

A Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is a branch of deep learning neural network which is developed to process and recognize images and other multidimensional data. It is developed by the structure and function of the human visual

technology, which can identify objects and its patterns in visual stimuli.

CNNs use several convolutional layers to extract features from query images or data, which are then transform through fully connected multiple layers to produce a prediction or classification. The convolutional layers use filters or kernels to convolve over the input data and extract features such as edges, lines, textures, and shapes. These features are then combined and passed through activation functions and pooling layers to reduce the dimensionality of the data and improve efficiency.

1. II. CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS

A convolutional neural network is mostly used for the purpose of image based processing like classification, detection, and image segmentation problems. The concept of a CNN consists of several layers of filters, called convolutional layers, which can extract features from the query image like color, height, width, resize and also and other features of the image.

The feature extraction process in a CNN is performed by several convolutional layers. Once their features are extracted by the convolutional layers, they are typically processed by one or more fully connected layers, which perform classification or regression tasks based on the extracted features.

In this neural network models using only a few lines of code, it is used to extract the features of the images from the predefined image datasets. CNN specify for Convolutional Neural Network. It is a branch of neural network which is mostly used in image and video recognition and classification tasks. CNNs are composed of several layers, they are convolutional layers, pooling layers, and other fully connected layers.

The Convolutional layers uses a mathematical operation called convolution which is used to extract features from images. The convolutional layer accepts the input image using a set of filters, also known as kernels, to develop a feature map. These filters detect specific patterns in the image, such as edges or corners, and the feature map highlights the locations where these patterns are detected.

The Pooling layers reduce the spatial dimensions of the feature maps by down sampling them. This helps to decrease the computational complexity of the network model and prevents overfitting.

The Fully connected layers are typically used at the end of the network model to classify the input image. They take the features extracted by the convolutional and pooling layers and output a probability distribution over the possible classes.

In this instance, we disregard a number of fully connected layers and focus just on the outcomes of the feature extraction.

The neural network depicted in [Fig 1] and in the [Fig 2] it witness an exemplary illustration of the convolutional neural network architecture, known as the LeNet-5. One of the remarkable attributes of CNNs is their proficiency to apprehend and deduce significant features from images through the utilization of convolutional layers. Convolutional layers are the building blocks of CNNs and are responsible for learning and extracting feature maps from images. The CNN composed of three types of layers:

Input Layer:

In the Convolutional Neural Network, the input layer is assigned for processing the query image and extracting features of that query image that will be transforms to subsequent layers to perform many complex tasks, such as classification or segmentation.

The input layer of a CNN is consists of a series of convolutional layers followed by several pooling layers. The input layers applies a set of filters to the query image, which helps to extract the features of the images such as edges, corners, and textures.

In a CNN, the input layer is essential for removing significant features from the input image data and preparing it for processing by later layers.

Hidden Layer:

The hidden layers are responsible for feature extraction. These layers use convolutional filters to scan the input image and extract different features at different scales. The extracted features are then passed through activation functions and pooling layers to further reduce their size and complexity.

The number of hidden layers in a CNN model can be different depending on the complexity of the problem and the size of the query data. Normally, a CNN model consists of several convolutional layers, followed by a pooling layer to decrease the spatial dimensions of the features, and then one or more fully connected layers to perform classification or regression based on the query images.

Output Layer:

The output layer for CNN normally consists of one or more fully connected layers it is also known as dense layers, that generates a vector of features for each query image. These features are then stored and it can be used for various tasks such as classification, object detection, or segmentation.

Generally, the working of an image search engine using CNN and DL involves accessing and preprocessing of the input data, and then extracting features using CNN, VGG16 (Visual Geometry Group 16) is a deep convolutional neural network (CNN) which is used here. The VGG16 generally consists of 16 layers, including 13 convolutional layers and 3 fully connected layers. The convolutional layers are arranged in sequential blocks, with each block containing multiple 3x3 convolutional layers followed by a pooling layer. The fully connected layers are at the end of the network process the output from the convolutional layers and produce the final classification predictions. Here we also use Keras it is designed to enable fast experimentation with deep neural networks and provides an easy-to-use interface for building and training models. Keras supports a wide range of neural network architectures indexing the feature vectors, querying the index to get the similar images, and ranking the results based on the similarity score.

2. III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Surbhi Jain et al. [1], The article image-based search engine using deep learning discusses the challenges of exploring image data on the World Wide Web (WWW) due to its voluminous nature and inability to be indexed by traditional text-based methods. Content-Based Image Retrieval (CBIR) has emerged as a solution, but it has been difficult to devise effective input methods and obtain adequate retrieval results due to the low-level nature of visible features in user input

images. The semantic gap between low-level pixel data and high-level human interpretation of image semantics is the main challenge in CBIR systems. Machine learning (ML) has been explored as a feasible way to reduce this gap, with deep learning methods such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) showing promise in improving feature representations and similarity measures.

The article focuses on the applications of CNNs model in classification and retrieval problems, with transfer learning using the GoogleNet deep architecture for retrieval of similar images. Each image's feature vectors were the final fully connected layer from the retrained GoogleNet CNN model, and Euclidean distances between these vectors and those of the query image were calculated to produce the dataset's closest matches. Overall, the article highlights the potential of CNNs and transfer learning in improving the performance of CBIR systems, especially in reducing the semantic gap between low-level visual features and high-level human interpretation of image semantics.

I Gede Susrama Mas Diyasa et al. [2], The article reverse image search analysis based on pre-trained convolutional neural network model discusses the use of Reverse Image Search (RIS), which is a type of Content-Based Image

Retrieval (CBIR), and how it can be used to search for information by inputting images as queries. The author uses a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model to extract image features from RIS results and compares the performance of the Pre-Trained CNN Model method with conventional methods such as perceptual hashing.

The author notes that the Pre-Trained CNN Model method can handle orientation information, which is a limitation of perceptual hashing. However, the Euclidean distance from the feature vector of several images was quite close, even though the images were different. This suggests that there may be some limitations to the effectiveness of the Pre-Trained CNN Model method.

Overall, the article provides insights into the potential of RIS and CBIR to improve the search experience for users. However, it also highlights the need for ongoing research to refine these methods and address their limitations.

Divya Ragatha Venkata et al. [3], The article image query based search engine using image content retrieval presents an interesting concept of using images as a query for search engines, which is becoming more popular in today's technology-driven world. This paper discusses the working of a image search engine model that enables customers to input images from their local database and then they got information about these images from the internet.

This paper express the challenges faces with using images as queries and how these challenges have been expressed through the proposed model. The use of image-based analysis and comparing techniques is presented as the solution to the

complexities involved in searching for information through query images.

The results of the study indicate that the proposed model is effective in extracting image content and retrieving relevant information. The use of this search engine model for product database searches is suggested as one of the most suitable applications.

Totally, the paper gives a valuable content to the field of image-based search techniques, and the developed model can have several practical implications. However, the article lacks wide technical and other informations on the working of the model, which would have been most useful for researchers and others.

Enescu Florentina Magda et al. [4], This paper compares different colour spaces and methods for colour image search using colour descriptors. The experiments are well-documented, and the results are presented clearly in charts and graphs. The study concludes that the HSV colour space performs better than other colour spaces, while RGB spaces provided poor results. The paper provides valuable insights for future research, but the study is limited to colour descriptors and does not explore other image features. Overall, the paper is informative and provides useful information on the performance of different colour spaces and methods for image search.

Kenji Kita et al. [5], This paper describes the implementation of an image search engine for the fashion industry using a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN). The authors trained their own CNN using a custom dataset and achieved high accuracy. They applied Euclidean and Cosine distances to implement a reverse search engine. The results showed that the accuracy and precision of the image search system depend on the accuracy of the trained CNN model. The paper provides valuable insights into the use of CNNs for image search and highlights the importance of accurate image features. Overall, the paper is informative and presents a useful approach to image search in the fashion industry.

3. IV.PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The system will start by conducting feature extraction on all images in the database and the query using a feature extraction algorithm which uses convolutional neural networks. This step involves analyzing and identifying the distinct attributes and characteristics of each image, which are then transformed into a set of numerical values representing the image features. Also we extract the features of query images which is used for the further indexing with the database images.

After extracting the features, the system will proceed to calculate the similarity between the query image and all the images in the database. This similarity calculation involves comparing the feature vectors of each image and quantifying their degree of similarity.

Upon receiving the query image, the system will commence a search for all images that bear a significant resemblance to it. These images will then be sorted and ranked based on their respective similarity scores, with the top-ranked ones being deemed as the best matches. This work flow is shown in the [Fig 3].

Fig 3

The images used for comparison is retrieved from the specific folder where all the database images stored in [Fig 4] we retrieve all the images to a specific folder and further this folder is used for its feature extraction.

Fig 4

By using convolutional neural networks and tensorflow the features of all images in the specific folder is extracted. Then the features of all images are stored into another folder in .npy format as in [Fig 5].

```

1 from tensorflow.keras.preprocessing import Image
2 from tensorflow.keras.applications.vgg16 import VGG16, preprocess_input
3 from tensorflow.keras.models import Model
4 import numpy as np
5
6 # See https://keras.io/applications/ for details
7
8 class FeatureExtractor:
9     def __init__(self) -> object:
10         base_model = VGG16(weights='imagenet')
11         self.model = Model(inputs=base_model.input, outputs=base_model.get_layer('fc3').output)
12
13     def extract(self, img):
14         """
15         Extract a deep feature from an input image
16         Args:
17             img: From PIL Image, open(path) or tensorflow.keras.preprocessing.image.load_img(path)
18         """
19         features = np.ndarray()
20         deep_features = self.model.predict(img)
21         img = img.resize((224, 224)) + VGG16.preprocess_input
22         img = img.convert('RGB') # Make sure img is color
23         img = image.img_to_array(img) # To np array, shape = (height, width, channels)
24
25         return features
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Fig 5

In order to compare the query image with the existing images, we must first extract the features from all of the images in the database and store them for later comparison. The query image is collected through user input and with the same feature extraction class the features of the query image is also extracted and stored to a folder for the reference. The query image is get through the user interface shown in the [Fig 6].

Fig 6

Euclidean distance is a commonly used distance metric in image feature comparison. In computer vision and image processing, features are often used to describe the characteristics of an image. Examples of features are colour, texture, shape, and size and others.

The comparison of two images based on their features, the Euclidean distance is used as a measure of similarity calculation between the images feature vectors. The The Euclidean distance can be computed by taking the square root of the total sum of squared differences between corresponding elements that exist in both feature vectors.

For finding similar images to a query image, we can calculate the distance between the query image and each image in the dataset using the Euclidean distance or l2 norm formula. If the resulting number is small, then the image is mostly similar to the query.

$$dist(q, img) = ||q - img||_2 = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (q_i - img_i)^2}$$

The variables used in this formula include q, which stands for the query, img, which stands for the image, n, which stands for the number of items in the feature vector, and i, which stands for the vector's location.

Finding similar images from a large collection of images is a frequent method of using the image search. Finding the images with the closest distances to the query image can be done by first calculating the distance between the feature vectors of each image in the collection.

The Feature vector is a collection of values that is extracted from an image. We use a several feature vector to represent an image's color histogram or other texture features. Once we generate a feature vector for an image, to assess how similar the images are, we can easily calculate the distance between these feature vectors and the features of the query image.

There are many distance metrics which can be used for calculating the distances between feature vectors of query image and the image in the image datasets, such as Euclidean distance, Manhattan distance, or others. In Python, we use NumPy libraries to perform these calculations effectively.

NumPy is a python library used for scientific computing that serves many functions and tools for working with arrays and other matrices. We can use NumPy to create and manipulate arrays of feature vectors, and then use its functions to calculate distances between these arrays.

The result image is typically displayed based on the distance calculated between the query image and a set of images which is stored in the specific folder. The top result is shown to be the images that are closest to the query image. And the distances of each images with corresponding to the query image is also displayed. If the query image is itself available in the image dataset then the displayed distance is 0 and as per the dissimilarities the distance value will vary accordingly. In the [Fig 7] shows the results similar for query image. Here we limited the results to shows the most similar ones and if there is no similar images is found then displayed as no result found. In [Fig 7] it shows most similar two images and the first image is exactly similar to the query image and have the distance 0.0 and second image have bit greater distance than first one.

Fig 7

4. V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, This paper describes a method that utilizes CNN, tensorflow, and numpy to find similar images. The technique relies on computing the Euclidean distance between images, and the top images with the smallest

distance are displayed. When the query image is already included in the existing image dataset, the method produces accurate results. However, if the query image is not similar to the dataset, the results may not be as accurate as well. Additionally, it should be noted that this technique does not always provide a accurate match for the query image. Instead, it displays the most similar images comparable to all image from the dataset.

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